

Vertical seismic absorber utilizing inertance and negative stiffness implemented with gas springs

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Abstract: A novel implementation of negative stiffness elements (NSEs) is proposed, utilizing industrial grade nitrogen gas springs as pre-stressed stiffness elements in a configuration with lever arms. This NSE is combined with an inerter to form a stiff dynamic absorber (SDA) for vertical seismic protection of structures with base isolation. The SDA is optimized to minimize vertical accelerations while ensuring static structural integrity, excellent damping performance and containment of relative displacements. The introduction of gas springs in place of conventional linear springs addresses important practical limitations through features of non-linearity and industrial grade manufacturing. The proposed implementation is dimensioned for a 50-ton structure and evaluated numerically for 25 actual earthquake records, in comparison with a linear SDA model and an equivalent conventional damper (CD). Individual and averaged results of acceleration and displacement time histories demonstrate vastly superior response compared to CD regarding induced accelerations for similar displacements. Performance equivalency with the linear SDA model indicates the stability of the gas spring implementation while guaranteeing predictability, tested endurance, proper tolerances, and off-axis motion resistance without requiring additional guiding components, as opposed to conventional springs. These features render the proposed implementation a promising solution for the realization of NSEs in seismic protection.

Keywords: negative stiffness; gas springs; vertical seismic protection; KDamper; inerter

1 Introduction

Among major environmental hazards, earthquakes constitute one of the most common and costly in damages to infrastructure and human lives. The generated ground motion, characterized by ultralow frequency components, induces damaging vibrations to structures and their contents. Other sources related to undesirable low-frequency ground motion include, among others, heavy or highspeed vehicles and construction activities. In recent years many earthquakes with vertical acceleration components at a level of 1 g have been recorded. The relationship between vertical and horizontal ground motions is intricate, and vertical excitation can leave a significant impact on seismic performance, as shown

by Wang *et al.* (2016) and Li *et al.* (2007). These facts highlight the importance of structural protection in vertical and horizontal directions.

The conventional approach of designing stiff and highly damped structures to address the imperative need for mitigation of such ground motions presents technical and financial constraints. Moreover, in some cases their dynamic behavior can be counter effective, resulting in amplification of ground acceleration transferred to the main structure.

The concept of isolation constitutes an alternative approach, as described by Naeim and Kelly (1999). Namely, a flexible layer is introduced between the structure and its base to alter the dynamic properties of the system and mitigate ground-induced vibrations. The basic principle is the reduction of the natural frequency of the system below the dominant energy-containing frequency components of ground motions, thus attenuating induced accelerations on a structure. However, since this is achieved through a decrease in the structural rigidity of the support, a fundamental conflict of requirements arises: the vertically isolated system is at risk of undergoing extreme deformations and static displacements, as the weight-bearing capacity of the structure is substantially compromised.

These constraints have motivated research on the development of various alternative strategies of vibration control, including tuned mass dampers (TMD); inerters,

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quasi-zero stiffness oscillators (QZS); and negative stiffness driven absorbers, such as the KDamper, among other devices.

The TMD concept is widely used in several engineering applications, including high-rise buildings and skyscrapers, as in the works of Luft and Rene (1979), Qin *et al.* (2009), and Ramezani *et al.* (2018), bridges, as in Debnath *et al.* (2016); and wind turbines, as in Chen and Georgakis (2015) and Bargi *et al.* (2016), among others. Additionally, this concept can be used for retrofitting conventional base isolators of structures to reduce induced displacement amplitudes, an approach taken by Hashimoto *et al.* (2015), Taniguchi *et al.* (2008), and Xiang and Nishitani (2014).

However, the TMD and related vibration absorption techniques engender two main disadvantages. The first is the requirement for heavy additional masses to provide significant attenuation. The second is the narrow-band effectiveness that these devices present, which renders them unsuitable for unpredictable broadband excitations and sensitive to detuning, as noted by Weber and Feltrin (2010).

The introduction of the inerter found in Chen and Smith (2009) and Smith (2002) provided a means to encounter the requirement of the TMD for heavy additional masses. This two-terminal element generates at its ends a force that is proportional to the relative acceleration at its terminals. Thus, it can provide an inertial effect (inertance) that is multiple times higher than the mass of the involved components. Regarding seismic isolation of buildings, several specific designs of the inerter have been introduced, as seen in De Domenico *et al.* (2019), De Domenico and Ricciardi (2018), Giaralis and Taflanidis (2018), Lazar *et al.* (2014), Saitoh (2012) and Pandey and Mishra (2021). However, several disadvantages of the inerter arise due to complexities in its implementation and the resulting reduction of the system's effective damping due to its higher effective mass. Especially in seismic isolation applications, the inerter can significantly enhance the transfer of base acceleration to the main structure compared to a highly damped conventional base isolator, as demonstrated by Kelly (1999).

A different approach for vibration absorbers, consists of the inclusion of negative stiffness elements (NSEs). In a spring-mass system, negative stiffness occurs when the ratio of change of the spring reactive force to mass displacement is such that resistance is decreased, hence the force generated by the spring is assisting in the spring deformation process, as opposed to the classic case of positive stiffness. The introduction of negative stiffness elements leads to a reduction of the overall stiffness of the system, thereby reducing its natural frequency. This way, the transmissibility of the system, which depends on the ratio of the system's natural frequency to the excitation frequency, is significantly reduced, resulting in enhanced isolation for a wider range of operating frequencies. The utilization of NSE

for vibration isolation was introduced in seminal works of Molyneux (1957) and Platus (1992). NSEs allow the reduction of a system's natural frequency to very low levels and have found applications in seismic isolation in the works of Attary *et al.* (2017), Ibrahim (2008), Iemura and Pradono (2009), Sarlis *et al.* (2013) and Pasala *et al.* (2012). This direction has been steadily gaining traction, a fact that is reflected in more recent advances, as in the works of Saha and Mishra (2019); Wang *et al.* (2018); Wang *et al.* (2019); Cimellaro *et al.* (2020); Nguyen *et al.* (2021); and Nepal and Saitoh (2020), all of which refer to optimization of existing concepts or the introduction of new implementations and applications.

Investigations regarding the optimal combination of inerter mechanisms with negative stiffness elements and an analysis of their combined performance for protection against earthquakes have been carried out by Wang *et al.* (2019) and Zhao *et al.* (2020), respectively.

A class of systems with NSE inclusions, QZS oscillators, have been proposed in the works of Carrella *et al.* (2007); Ye *et al.* (2021); and Chang *et al.* (2021) and further explored for application in the field of seismic protection for the attenuation of the dynamic forces imposed on the structure. QZS oscillators combine a static stiffness that sufficiently high to bear the structural weight, with a low dynamic stiffness that significantly reduces isolation frequency. Their downside, however, lies in limited damping capacity along with a high sensitivity to variations of the seismic load.

The stiff dynamic absorber (SDA), as introduced in Kapasakalis *et al.* (2021) and investigated in this work, belongs to the family of the KDamper concept, the framework of which was established in Antoniadis *et al.* (2015) and Antoniadis *et al.* (2018). The KDamper is another class of negative stiffness-based vibration absorbers. It is essentially an extension of the TMD with the inclusion of a negative stiffness element. The phase difference between the positive and negative elastic forces results in an additional inertial effect on the internal mass of the TMD. Consequently, the value of the NSE dictates the performance of the system which by extension avoids the requirement of heavy additional mass. Additionally, the KDamper demonstrates significantly higher modal damping than the TMD and achieves greater attenuation in a wider frequency band. Moreover, its design retains the high static/low dynamic stiffness feature of the QZS, oscillators while the optimal selection of the individual stiffness elements makes it easy to customize.

This flexibility enabled the development of other KDamper variants and extensions for several different applications in the fields of seismic protection of various types of structures, as demonstrated in Kapasakalis *et al.* (2017, 2020); vibration absorption of machinery, as in Paradeisiotis, Tsioumanis, Antoniadis and Fouriki (2020); and noise control, as in Paradeisiotis *et al.* (2021).

The original KDamper was optimized for minimization of the displacement amplitude of the

seismic mass and has been investigated as such for seismic protection applications. This approach drastically reduces the relative displacement of the structure while maintaining its absolute acceleration within reasonable limits.

The SDA variant is different in that it includes an inerter within the system and is optimized for the minimization of the induced absolute acceleration on the structure while retaining displacement within acceptable levels. Moreover, static stiffness can be tuned according to requirements, depending on the initial static equilibrium position of the configuration, while dynamic stiffness is kept low enough to achieve a desired reduction of the natural frequency. The impact of an inerter between the structure and the base was tested by Kalogerakou *et al.* (2022) across a sample of EC-compatible artificial earthquakes and was shown to substantially assist in the control of displacements of the seismic and internal masses.

Various implementations of the NSE have been investigated throughout the above-cited references of the KDamper and its variants, including the use of disc springs, pre-stressed helical springs in various configurations, curved beams, and more.

Recurring issues with these designs are related to the performance of the NSE and on practical constraints during implementation. Requirements of high negative stiffness values or large displacements of the internal mass can lead to undesired buckling deformation and impose off-axis bending loads. Moreover, several highly accurate guiding mechanisms and other moving parts are required to impose necessary kinematic constraints, creating a complex and difficult-to-construct configuration. Finally, designs with conventional coil springs can provide desired negative stiffness only in a narrow range of displacements relative to their characteristic dimensions.

To overcome many of these challenges, this work proposes the utilization of standardized industrial-grade nitrogen gas springs in place of conventional coil springs — or other linear stiffness elements — for the implementation of the NSE. Due to their industrial nature, gas springs provide the required predictability of performance, tested endurance features, and high tolerances while also meeting the important need for high off-axis motion resistance without requiring additional guiding components. Also, as demonstrated in the following sections, the type of non-linear behavior that is specific to gas springs provides undiminished negative stiffness value for the entire stroke and large displacement range. One example of the application of gas springs utilized in a TMD system can be found in Nagarajaiah (2009).

Section 2 describes in summary form the basic operational principles and involved design parameters of the SDA, along with a brief explanation of the procedure for the optimal selection of these parameters.

In Sec. 3 the NSE configuration is analyzed. Some of

the previously mentioned limitations of coil springs and corresponding advantages associated with the proposed gas springs are discussed in further detail. Following a brief citation of the basic gas spring theory, a parametric investigation of the gas spring-NSE implementation is carried out.

Subsequently, in Sec. 4 a case study of a 50 t structure subject to vertical ground motion is presented. The optimal set of SDA parameters is selected based on the analysis of Kalogerakou *et al.* (2022), followed by the appropriate dimensioning of the NSE and its elements and an analysis of the corresponding force and stiffness behavior.

Finally, in Sec. 5, the performance of the proposed SDA implementation is evaluated through a series of numerical simulations for 25 actual earthquake records. Results include average acceleration and displacement ratios from corresponding time histories and are compared with a linear model of the SDA and an equivalent conventional damper (CD).

The results demonstrate that the SDA implemented with gas springs shows a vastly superior performance over the CD regarding accelerations, and slightly better behavior for displacements. Meanwhile, in comparison to the linear SDA model, the performance is almost identical across the examined earthquake cases. This indicates the ability of the gas spring implementation to accommodate large displacements caused by extreme earthquakes without significant deviation from the ideal scenario of constant negative stiffness and without running into issues of instability.

2 Stiff dynamic absorber (SDA)

Figure 1 contains the notation for the lumped parameter models of a conventional vibration damper (CD) and the proposed stiff dynamic absorber (SDA) while considering the base excitation of the system.

2.1 Theoretical background

The natural frequency of a CD, as shown in Fig. 1(a), is denoted by f_R which is expressed as:

$$f_R = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k_R}{m_S}} \quad (1)$$

The vertical static deflection of the CD can be expressed as a function of solely its natural frequency f_R and the acceleration of gravity g as follows:

$$X_{\text{vsd}} = \frac{m_S g}{k_R} = \frac{g}{(2\pi f_R)^2} \quad (2)$$

This relationship highlights the underlying constraints

Fig. 1 Lumped parameter models with base excitation.
(a) Conventional damper (CD); (b) SDA

of low-frequency vibration isolation in the vertical direction.

The SDA can be seen as retrofitting an existing reference CD with additional elements, including a negative stiffness element (NSE). However, the SDA receives static loading prior to the connection of additional elements. Namely, the original stiffness element with value k_R bears the weight of the seismic mass, whereas the remainder of the elements are connected at the resulting equilibrium position of the system. In this manner, the two compared systems are equivalent in terms of vertical static deflection and static loading bearing capacity.

Denoted by k_0 , the “dynamic” stiffness of the SDA is calculated as:

$$k_0 = k_R + \frac{k_p k_N}{k_p + k_N} = k_R + k_I \quad (3)$$

Therefore, a nominal frequency for the SDA, including the inerter, may be defined as

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k_0}{m_s + b_R}} \quad (4)$$

which can be lower than the natural frequency f_R of the reference system, since for $k_p > k_N$ the term k_I is negative, thus reducing total stiffness due to the inerter b_R , which increases the inertia of the system.

Furthermore, to ensure that the stability condition of the system is satisfied ($k_0 > 0$), possible variations of the k_R , k_p , and k_N stiffness elements due to material fatigue, manufacturing tolerances, non-linear behavior, and temperature fluctuations, are considered during the optimization procedure of the SDA. These stability margins are imposed via the introduction of the tolerances ε_R , ε_p , ε_N respectively, so that limiting values of the stiffness elements can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} k_{R\text{lim}} &= (1 - \varepsilon_R) k_R \\ k_{p\text{lim}} &= (1 - \varepsilon_p) k_p \\ k_{N\text{lim}} &= (1 + \varepsilon_N) k_N \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Because of the stability condition, and accounting for these tolerances, the value of the k_p stiffness element is calculated as:

$$k_p = \frac{-(1 - \varepsilon_R)(1 + \varepsilon_N) k_N}{(1 - \varepsilon_p) \left[(1 - \varepsilon_R) + (1 + \varepsilon_N) \frac{k_N}{k_R} \right]} \quad (6)$$

while the neutral stability position is:

$$k_{NL} = \frac{-k_R k_p}{k_R + k_p} \quad (7)$$

representing the maximum permissible value — in absolute terms — of the negative stiffness element.

2.2 Equation of motion

For the considered case of base excitation, the displacements relative to the base are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} u_s &= x_s - x_G \\ u_D &= x_D - x_G \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, relative velocities and accelerations are defined. Next, the equation of motion of the SDA in matrix notation is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F}a_G(t) \quad (9)$$

where the mass, damping, stiffness, and excitation matrices are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M} &= \begin{bmatrix} m_s + b_R & 0 \\ 0 & m_D \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{C} &= \begin{bmatrix} c_R + c_p & -c_p \\ -c_p & c_p + c_N \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{K} &= \begin{bmatrix} k_R + k_p & -k_p \\ -k_p & k_p + k_N \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{F} &= - \begin{Bmatrix} m_s \\ m_D \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and the acceleration of the base $a_G = \ddot{x}_G$ is the time dependent excitation of the system.

2.3 Frequency response

Considering the case of harmonic excitation, the base acceleration is taken in the form

$$a_G(t) = \tilde{A}_G e^{j\Omega t} \quad (11)$$

where \tilde{A}_G is the complex amplitude and Ω the excitation frequency. Consequently, the displacements will be of the form $u(t) = \tilde{U}e^{j\Omega t}$ and substituting this form of the solution, the transfer matrix of the system is calculated from (12):

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}} = \begin{bmatrix} -\Omega^2(m_s + b_r) + j\Omega c_p + k_r + k_p - (j\Omega c_p + k_p) \\ -(j\Omega c_p + k_p) - \Omega^2 m_D + j\Omega(c_p + c_N) + k_p + k_N \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Thus, the corresponding transfer functions of the relative displacement amplitudes over the base acceleration amplitude come as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{H}_{US} \\ \tilde{H}_{UD} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{U}_S \\ \tilde{U}_D \\ \tilde{A}_G \end{Bmatrix} = \tilde{\mathbf{H}}^{-1} \mathbf{F} \quad (13)$$

Additionally, the transfer functions of the absolute accelerations of the seismic and internal masses may then be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{H}_{AS} &= \frac{\tilde{A}_S}{\tilde{A}_G} = 1 - \Omega^2 \tilde{H}_{US} \\ \tilde{H}_{AD} &= \frac{\tilde{A}_D}{\tilde{A}_G} = 1 - \Omega^2 \tilde{H}_{UD} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

2.4 Optimization

The values of the SDA elements are selected based on the results of the optimization procedure presented in Kalogerakou *et al.* (2021). In summary, it was shown that the formula for the objective function yielding the best results regarding the average and peak absolute acceleration of the seismic mass was:

$$Q_{AS} = \int_{\Omega_1}^{\Omega_2} |\tilde{H}_{AS}(\omega)|^2 d\Omega \quad (15)$$

This value represents the area below the transfer function of the acceleration of the seismic mass in a selected frequency range $\Omega \in [\Omega_1, \Omega_2]$. Therefore, it is essentially a measure of the transmissibility of the system. Hence, it also is an accurate indicator of the portion of energy that is transferred to the structure as absolute acceleration, and consequently, of the magnitude of the expected force reactions borne by the structure during an earthquake. Moreover, this quantity is independent of the external excitation, thus it is more convenient as an objective function in comparison to other approaches, for example, RMS quantities of PSDs that are functions of the ground motion acceleration PSD, as in Kapsakalis *et al.* .

3 NSE Implementation

The fundamental configuration of horizontal pre-stressed stiffness elements with a lever arm for the realization of the NSE, in the context of the original KDamper, was introduced in Antoniadis *et al.* (2018). However, the use of conventional springs as the horizontal elastic elements generates certain practical challenges and limitations in performance.

First, the design requirements regarding stroke and stiffness of the elastic elements incorporated in the NSE configuration impose strict constraints on the dimensions of coil springs. This is especially important in cases such as seismic isolation, where the displacements of the internal degree of freedom are significant. Bulky and slender springs are commonly required, thereby inducing considerable stresses in these components. This can in turn create further consequences such as vulnerability to buckling deformation. Since the direction of the internal force is vertical to the primary axis of the compression of elastic elements, these off-axis components induce bending loads. In can be seen in Fig. 2, large displacements along the y -axis may impose a bending moment over the z -axis and hence induce buckling of the stiffness element.

A second tightly associated consideration is the requirement of an accurate alignment of the opposing acting stiffness elements and generally high tolerances of the involved components. Namely, even slight imbalances of various loads can significantly reduce the generated negative stiffness of the configuration, and hence the general performance of the absorber. To encounter these issues, several highly accurate guiding mechanisms and other moving parts are required to impose the necessary kinematic constraints. This greatly increases the complexity of the implementation and the need for accurate tuning, which down the line also leads to increased construction and maintenance costs, along with many possible points of failure.

Lastly, the incorporation of conventional stiffness elements with generally linear elastic behavior results in rapidly decreasing negative stiffness values (in absolute terms) for large displacements relative to the

Fig. 2 NSE configuration half model

equilibrium position of the configuration, as demonstrated in Fig. 7. In all, this increases the required dimensions of the configuration and leads to a reduced range of optimal performance of the absorber.

This work proposes the utilization of standardized industrial grade nitrogen gas springs in place of horizontal coil springs, as these combine several features that address most of the challenges described above. First, they provide the required predictability of performance, tested endurance features, and high tolerances due to their industrial nature. Also, gas springs can accommodate the massive forces, high stiffness, and stroke requirements of such an implementation in a relatively compact package, which can be embedded in the foundation of a building, as implied by this example. Moreover, gas springs meet the need for high off-axis motion resistance, meaning that relative to the primary compression axis, their bending and torsional stiffness is much higher. This allows the elimination of guiding elements required in the case of, for instance, coil springs, thereby reducing the number of moving parts thus simplifying the assembly and ensuring proper kinematic constraints and optimal performance. Lastly, as will be shown in Sec. 3.1, a type of non-linear behavior that is specific to that of gas springs provides an undiminished negative stiffness value for the entire stroke, ensuring satisfactory and reliable performance for a large displacement range.

3.1 Kinematic analysis

A half model representing the working principle of the NSE configuration is shown in Fig. 2. Its complete implementation is symmetric for the yz plane; that is, two elastic elements are used, and accordingly, the two lever arms are jointed in the place of the roller boundary condition along the y -axis.

The maximum compression of the elastic element is denoted by s_0 , which later will be associated with the nominal stroke of the gas spring. At maximum compression, corresponding to the horizontal position of the lever arm, the stiffness of this element is denoted by k_{s_0} . Additionally, this position corresponds to the nominal resulting negative stiffness value in the vertical direction denoted by k_{N_0} . The initial length of the horizontal elastic element is denoted by l_{HI} (in general the subscript association is H-Horizontal, I-Initial, 0-horizontal position of lever arm / unstable equilibrium position).

A non-dimensional parameter c_1 is defined as:

$$c_1 = \frac{b - l_{HI}}{a} = 1 - \frac{s_0}{a} \quad (16)$$

which relates to the basic geometric parameters of the configuration. Other useful geometrical relations are:

$$a_x = \sqrt{a^2 - u^2} \quad (17)$$

$$\tan \phi = \frac{u}{a_x} \quad (18)$$

$$l_H(u) = b - a_x \quad (19)$$

whereby $l_H(u)$, the variable length of the horizontal stiffness element, is denoted during the movement of the lever arm. The geometric relationship between the vertical displacement u and the stroke s of the elastic element, are shown as:

$$s(u) = a_x(u) - c_1 a = a(\cos \phi - c_1) \quad (20)$$

and at maximum stroke holds that $s_0 = a(1 - c_1)$.

The range of movement is defined by the initial position u_1 , where the horizontal elastic element has its initial length l_{HI} , as $u = \pm u_1$. Consequently:

$$u_1 = a\sqrt{1 - c_1^2} \quad (21)$$

which, considering the initial angle ϕ_1 , also leads to:

$$\tan \phi_1 = \frac{u_1}{\sqrt{a^2 - u_1^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{c_1^2} - 1} \quad (22)$$

3.2 Basic gas spring theory

The main components of a gas spring are a cylinder, a piston rod, a seal, and a guide. These devices utilize the compressibility of an enclosed gas — usually nitrogen — for heavy load industrial applications, to induce piston motion by a force proportional to the piston's displacement.

It is known that periodic piston motion results in a net heat transfer to the walls of the enclosure due to gas viscosity and other friction effects. This in turn results in a finite amount of energy dissipation corresponding to a hysteretic behavior, meaning that the force-displacement curves of a gas spring follow different paths between extension and compression, as discussed in Mirels (1994), Bauwens (1996), and Kornhauser and Smith (1993). Essentially, the output force is the sum of an elastic and a damping force, per Chen *et al.* (2020).

However, for the purposes of an initial evaluation of the concept and simplification of the analysis, it is assumed that gas viscosity and heat conduction effects are neglected. This is reflected in the force equations and that a damping coefficient is not considered for the gas springs. Therefore, during this investigation

the temperature inside the gas spring is considered as remaining constant during the stroke. In most cases the process is not isothermal but polytropic, which affects the true force. Depending on the operating frequency of the gas spring and the initial gas pressure, the polytropic exponent may vary between 1 and 1.55, as mentioned in KALLER (2010) and Löcken and Welsch (2015).

In contrast to most other types of springs, gas springs have a built-in pre-tension force that leads to a relatively flat characteristic force curve. On one hand, this means the difference in force between full extension and compression is comparatively small. On the other hand, this enables greater stroke for these smaller variations in force. Design features of gas springs, such as a large energy-storage capacity per unit volume, has established them as a popular choice in low-frequency applications in which usually the requirements combine large static deflections and load-carrying capacity, as seen in Nguyen *et al.* (2021), and Del Fabbro, *et al.* (1988).

The exerted force F_s of a gas spring as a function of the seal stroke s , is calculated from the expression provided by KALLER (2010):

$$F_s(s) = \frac{F_1}{(1 - s/s_n)^n} \quad (23)$$

where

$$s_n = \frac{s_0}{1 - (F_1/F_0)^{1/n}} \quad (24)$$

and n is the polytropic coefficient, s_0 is the nominal (maximum) stroke, $F_0 = F_s(s_0)$ is the maximum force, and F_1 is the initial (nominal) force. The derivative of the force regarding the stroke gives the equivalent stiffness of the gas spring, as:

$$k_s(s) = \frac{n}{s_n} \frac{1}{(1 - s/s_n)^{n+1}} F_s(s) \quad (25)$$

Therefore, the maximum stiffness value of the gas spring ($s = s_0$) comes as:

$$k_{s_0} = n \frac{F_0}{s_0} \left[\left(\frac{F_0}{F_1} \right)^{1/n} - 1 \right] \quad (26)$$

The gas spring is filled at an initial charging pressure p_{charg} , which relates to the initial force by the approximate expression:

$$F_1 \approx p_{\text{charg}} \frac{\pi d^2}{40} \quad (27)$$

where d is the dynamic seal diameter. The slope $\pi d^2 / 40$ might be slightly different if given otherwise by the manufacturer. Regarding the maximum force F_0 at a nominal stroke, manufacturers usually provide a pressure rise factor, or equivalent force diagrams versus stroke. Therefore, a relation between the initial and maximum forces can be extracted in the form of a ratio $\lambda = F_0 / F_1$ between maximum and initial forces.

3.3 Vertical force and stiffness

Since from now on it is considered that the horizontal elastic elements are represented by gas springs, the expressions of force and equivalent stiffness along the line of action (vertical direction) differ from those in past literature. The resulting vertical force of the configuration is calculated as:

$$F_N(u) = -F_s(s) \tan \phi \quad (28)$$

and the equivalent stiffness comes by derivation as to the vertical displacement u , ($s = s(u)$):

$$k_N(u) = \frac{\partial F_N}{\partial u} = k_s(s) \tan^2 \phi - \frac{F_s(s)}{a_x} \sec^2 \phi \\ = \left\{ n \left[\frac{1 - c_1 \lambda^{-1/n}}{1 - \lambda^{-1/n}} - \cos \phi \right]^{-1} \tan^2 \phi - \sec^3 \phi \right\} \frac{F_s(s)}{a} \quad (29)$$

Therefore, at the horizontal position of the lever arm ($u = 0$), the stiffness value k_{N0} becomes:

$$k_{N0} = -\frac{F_0}{a} = -\frac{\lambda F_1}{a} \quad (30)$$

This means that for a selected gas spring, the only parameter of the NSE configuration that defines the value of k_{N0} is the length ϕ of the lever arm. Obviously, the value of k_{N0} must be as close as possible to the value of k_N , resulting from the dimensioning of the SDA.

3.4 Parametric analysis

The maximum vertical force results when $\phi = \phi_1$, and since $\tan \phi$ is essentially a coefficient of the gas spring force, from Eq. (28), $\tan \phi_1$ can be used as an indicator of the level of the vertical force as a function of parameter c_1 .

Additionally, from the dimensioning of the SDA, the minimum permissible value of negative stiffness k_{N1} related to the stability condition imposes a maximum permissible amplitude u_1 for the displacement of the internal degree of freedom, which corresponds to the added mass to which the NSE is connected. Therefore, the range of movement of the lever arm $\pm u_1$ must be

able to physically accommodate this amplitude, namely, $u_L < u_1$. Also, ideally the negative stiffness value must be relatively constant in the range of $u = \pm u_L$.

To quantify the “quality” of the configuration regarding the above requirement, an additional parameter δ is defined. This parameter is the ratio of the vertical stiffness at the characteristic displacement u_L relative to maximum negative stiffness. Therefore, as $\delta \rightarrow 1$, the resulting negative stiffness value remains close to the nominal value in that displacement range. For the purposes of the parametric analysis, this parameter is defined as δ_1 , corresponding to the maximum displacement u_1 where $s = 0$, as follows:

$$\delta_1 = \frac{k_{NL}}{k_{N0}} = \frac{1}{\lambda c_1^2} \left[\frac{1}{c_1} - n(1 - \lambda^{-1/n}) \frac{1 - c_1^2}{1 - c_1} \right] \quad (31)$$

Meanwhile, at the maximum permissible displacement $u = u_L$, where $s_L = (a^2 - u_L^2)^{1/2} - a c_1$:

$$\delta = \frac{k_{NL}}{k_{N0}} = \frac{F_s(s_L)}{(a^2 - u_L^2)} \left[\frac{n u_L^2}{s_n(1 - s_L/s_n)} - \frac{a}{\sqrt{1 - (u_L^2/a)^2}} \right] \quad (32)$$

As shown in Fig. 3(a) the parametric investigation for $c_1 = 0:1$ shows that as c_1 increases, the displacement range relative to the lever arm length decreases, along with the maximum vertical force. Moreover, $\delta \rightarrow 1$, while it also surpasses unity when $c_1 \rightarrow 1$.

Further, as apparent from Fig. 3(b), which is the bracketed expression in Eq. (29) for a given (λ, n) pair as a function of ϕ , the resulting vertical stiffness is always negative and decreases rapidly at large angles. Another consequence of this behavior is that the geometrical requirement $u_1 > u_L$ alone does not guarantee safeperation since at displacement u_L the resulting value of k_N must not exceed k_{NL} . If u_L is approximately known, for example, from linear simulations of the SDA (namely with $k_N = \text{const}$), then from Eq. (32) it can inform the quality of the configuration and by extension the selection of the gas spring. Inversely, from a given value of k_{NL} , the maximum permissible displacement can be calculated by solving Eq.(32) for u_L .

4 Case study

In this section, an optimal set of SDA parameters is selected. Considering a specific seismic mass, the various elements are calculated, and the resulting transfer

functions are briefly presented. Then, the individual performance of the NSE with gas springs for this case study is examined, before moving to Sec. 5, in which the results of the complete simulations are presented.

4.1 Optimal SDA parameters

The SDA optimization method in discussed in detail in Sec. 3 of Kalogerakou *et al.* (2022), while in Sec. 4 the optimal sets of parameters were calculated for three cases of X_{vsd} , namely, for configurations with increasing static stiffness k_R .

For the purposes of this examination, the opted set of parameters corresponds to the case of $X_{vsd} = 20$ mm and is accompanied by the set of fixed parameters summarized in Table 1.

The constraints of the optimization problem concerned the value of the negative stiffness coefficient κ_N (stiffness coefficients denoted with Greek “kappa”), the inertance ratio μ_R , and the damping ratios $\zeta_R, \zeta_P, \zeta_N$. Specifically:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_N &\in [0, -800] \left[\frac{\text{kN/m}}{\text{t}} \right] \\ \mu_R &\in [0, 100] [\%] \\ \zeta_R, \zeta_P, \zeta_N &\in [0, 2] [\%] \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 3 Parametric investigation of c_1 . (a) Relevant non-dimensional parameters; (b) Non-dimensional stiffness curves

The negative stiffness coefficient is given in $\frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}} \equiv \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}}$ per unit (ton) of seismic mass, and similarly the damping coefficients in $\frac{\text{kNs}}{\text{m}} \equiv \frac{\text{Ns}}{\text{mm}}$ per unit (ton) of seismic mass, so that for $i = \text{R, P, N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} k_i &= \kappa_i m_s \\ c_i &= 2\zeta_i \sqrt{k_R m_s} = \bar{c}_i m_s \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

while

$$\begin{aligned} m_D &= \mu_D m_s \\ b_R &= \mu_R m_s \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

The set of optimal parameters for the case of $X_{\text{vsd}} = 20$ mm is presented in Table 2.

The depended coefficients resulting from the selected optimal set are summarized in Table 3.

For this case study, a seismic mass of $m_s = 50$ ton is considered. Relevant values of the system based in the above sets of optimal coefficients are presented in Table 4. The value of f_0 in comparison to f_R indicates a reduction of the natural frequency of the reference CD system of about 45%. Besides the added mass and the inertance, the required value of the NSE is cited here along with its marginal value from Eq. (7).

Figures 4 and 5 present the transfer functions of Eqs. (13) and (14), respectively, for the above optimized set of values in comparison with the reference CD. The value of the damping element c of the conventional damper is calculated as in Eq. (33), where the damping ratio is taken as $\zeta = 15\%$, much higher than the damping

Table 1 Fixed parameters during the SDA optimization

X_{vsd} (mm)	μ_D (%)	ε_R (%)	ε_P (%)	ε_N (%)
20	5	5	5	10

Table 2 Optimal parameters of SDA

κ_N (kN/m/ton)	μ_R (%)	$\zeta_R = \zeta_P = \zeta_N$ (%)
-86.45	43.1	2

Table 3 Resulting coefficients of SDA

κ_R (kN/m/ton)	κ_P (kN/m/ton)	$\bar{c}_R = \bar{c}_P = \bar{c}_N$ (kNs/m/tn)
490.5	125.766	0.884

Table 4 Characteristic parameters of SDA for 50 ton seismic mass

f_0 (Hz)	f_R (Hz)	m_D (ton)	b_R (ton)	k_N (kN/m)	k_{NL} (kN/m)
1.946	3.525	2.5	21.55	-4322.5	-5005

elements of the SDA.

From the observation of these frequency response functions, it is expected that the two systems will perform similarly in terms of relative displacements of the seismic mass. However, regarding the absolute accelerations, the SDA promises vastly superior attenuation relative to the ground motion. These figures also demonstrate the amplified motion of the SDA's internal mass, which participates in the absorption of kinetic energy from the seismic structure. This can also indicate the level of expected displacement amplitude of the internal degree of freedom, which is essential for the design of the NSE implementation.

4.2 NSE dimensioning

For the realization of the horizontal elastic elements, the gas spring with the parameters summarized in Table 5 is selected from KALLER (2021). Then, the length of the lever arm results as $a = 152$ mm from Eq. (30) and the required $k_{N0} \equiv k_N$ value, considering that two such springs are utilized in the NSE configuration.

This specific gas spring is rated at 20000 daN for a charging pressure of 150 bar, while the diameter of the piston rod is 130 mm. Assuming isothermal compression ($n=1$), the parameters of the NSE configuration are summarized in Table 6.

To highlight the properties of the gas spring in this NSE configuration, a comparison is made with a case

Fig. 4 Transfer functions of relative displacement over base acceleration. Comparison with CD

Fig. 5 Transfer functions of absolute acceleration of seismic mass over base acceleration. Comparison with CD

in which the horizontal elastic element is linear, with a constant stiffness of $k_{S,lin}$. For the comparison to be equivalent, it holds that

$$k_{S,lin} = \frac{k_{N0}}{(c_1 - 1)} = -\frac{a}{s_0} k_{N0} \quad (35)$$

where k_{N0} is the same as in the gas spring implementation.

By applying a vertical displacement of the lever arm in the range $u \in [-u_L, u_L]$, the operation of the NSE configuration can be examined. Figure 6 shows a comparison of the exerted vertical force of the NSE configuration for two cases. The black line denotes the implementation of the horizontal elastic element via the gas spring. The red line represents an implementation with a linear spring ($k_{S,lin}$).

The various characteristic forces of the configuration are summarized in Table 7. The maximum vertical exerted force, essentially the force that would be required for the pre-stress of the elastic element, is almost four times higher than in the case of the linear spring. However, since in a real-world implementation pre-stress is applied horizontally, the required force is the same in both cases. At position u_L , the corresponding vertical force is only 13.47% higher in the gas spring implementation.

Figure 7 presents the corresponding comparison of the equivalent stiffness of the NSE configuration. The relevant values are presented in Table 8. For an implementation with a linear spring to achieve values of the δ parameter close to unity, it would require that $c_1 \rightarrow 0$, which also means that $s_0 \rightarrow a$. However, the lever arm length a can only be decreased up to a certain point to be able to accommodate the required bearings for the hinges.

Consequently, a much larger stroke would be needed and by extension a narrow (stiffer) and long helical spring to satisfy these requirements. Additionally, the gas spring implementation provides negative stiffness in the entirety of the displacement range due to the characteristic initial force F_I . Meanwhile, deviations around the horizontal position result in an even higher absolute value of k_N , as indicated by $\delta_{gs} > 100\%$, which is impossible with conventional linear springs.

It is important to reiterate that the k_{NL} stability condition imposes a maximum displacement permissible amplitude $[-u_L, +u_L]$, as shown in Figs. 7 and 8. Depending on the expected excitations and corresponding risk-assessment profile, the presence of hard-stoppers can be considered to ensure that these limits are not exceeded.

Figure 8 shows the total horizontal force and stiffness of the two gas springs as a function of the stroke within the range $s \in [0, s_0]$, which corresponds to the range $u \in [-u_L, u_L]$ of vertical displacement of the lever arm.

Finally, Fig. 9 presents the variation of the total length of the gas spring, along with its stroke corresponding to the applied range of vertical displacement u of the lever

arm. Again, this level of stroke to initial length is very difficult to achieve when using conventional springs without running into issues like buckling, unpredictable stiffness response and misalignments between the opposite springs in the absence of extremely accurate guiding.

Table 5 Gas spring parameters (2487.12.20000.125, Powerline)

s_0 (mm)	l_{HI} (mm)	H_I (N)	λ	n
125	360	1.9910×10^5	1.65	1

Table 6 NSE Configuration parameters

a (mm)	b (mm)	c_1	ϕ_1 ($^\circ$)	u_L (mm)	u_L (mm)
152	387	0.18	79.77	149.58	73

Table 7 Characteristic forces of NSE configuration

F_0 (kN)	$F_{Nmax,gs}$ (kN)	$F_{Nmax,lin}$ (kN)	$F_{N,gs}(u_L)$ (kN)	$F_{N,lin}(u_L)$ (kN)
657	2206.1	451.9	418.8	369.1

Table 8 Performance of the NSE configuration

k_{N0} (N/mm)	k_{s0} (N/mm)	$k_{s,lin}$ (N/mm)	δ_{gs} (%)	δ_{lin} (%)
-4.323×10^3	3.417×10^3	5.256×10^3	133.59	80.33

Fig. 6 Exerted vertical force of the NSE configuration. Comparison between gas spring and linear spring implementations

Fig. 7 Equivalent stiffness of the NSE configuration. Comparison between gas spring and linear spring implementations

5 Results

To evaluate the performance of the SDA with the gas spring-implemented NSE, a series of numerical simulations is carried out, using as the base excitation the accelerograms of 25 actual earthquake records, the details of which are presented in Table A1 in the Appendix. The corresponding model is labeled “SDA NLN”, indicating the non-linear nature of the NSE implementation. Additionally, a single degree of freedom model for the conventional damper labeled “CD” and a linear model of the SDA labeled “SDA LIN” are simultaneously simulated to draw the necessary comparisons. For clarification, the linear SDA model corresponds to an idealized case in which the negative stiffness value of the k_N element remains constant and is independent of the internal displacement. Therefore, it does not reflect a particular implementation of the NSE but rather a reference performance level of the SDA.

5.1 Summarized results

First, summarized results are presented in Fig. 10 regarding the peak absolute acceleration A_s of the seismic mass to PGA (peak ground acceleration) ratios and the peak relative displacement of the seismic mass, denoted by U_s to the vertical static displacement X_{vsd} ratios for all 25 records. The values of these ratios are

presented as percentages.

Observation of Fig. 10 indicates that the SDA performs better than the CD regarding induced acceleration in each of the simulated earthquakes. The SDA can reach ratios as low as 35%, as in the most extreme case of Earthquake No. 3 (Imperial Valley, 1979). In the most demanding cases, the discrepancies are even more apparent relative to the CD. For example, during Earthquake No. 13 (Northridge-Tarzana, 1978), the ratio of the SDA is almost three times lower than the CD.

From Fig. 11, however, the conclusions are not so straightforward as for the acceleration ratios. The CD is slightly more effective in containing the relative displacement of the seismic mass in many of the simulated cases. This is especially the case for earthquakes with higher energy in the very low frequency range, which corresponds to the stiffness region of the isolator, although both approaches present generally acceptable mitigation. However, in extreme, cases such as the No. 13 Northridge-Tarzana or the No. 10 (Northridge-Rinaldi, 1994), the CD cannot cope with the intensity of the excitation; meanwhile, the SDA is successful in containing these extremes. This can be explained by the coincidence of the dominant frequencies of these earthquakes with the resonant frequency of the CD and the fact that the SDA has a reduced resonant frequency due to its lower dynamic stiffness.

The averages of these ratios for the 25 records are presented in Figs. 12 and 13, for the accelerations and displacements, respectively.

On average, the acceleration ratio of the SDA is two times lower than for the CD, specifically, 50.3%, revalidating the conclusion from the individual results. The CD actually amplifies the PGA, with the induced acceleration on the structure 14.6% higher, on average, than the PGA. The impressive amplification of relative displacement for the CD in the case of No. 13 can be attributed to the dominant frequency of the excitation (4.6 Hz from Table A1 in Appendix) is relatively close to the CD’s resonant frequency (3.525 Hz from Table 4). Hence, the CD amplifies ground motion, resulting in an excessive structure relative displacement. Conversely, as can be confirmed by Fig. 11, the SDA manages to contain the structure’s relative displacement within a reasonable limit ($\approx 120\%$ of X_{vsd} or ≈ 2.5 cm in absolute terms). Additionally, the comparison of averages between the linear model and the non-linear gas spring SDA shows that their performance difference is not discernible.

The non-linear model gives slightly better results. This can be explained by the deviations of the k_N value from the design value in the gas spring NSE implementation, resulting in higher k_N values in absolute terms. Therefore, the deviations during operation correspond to increased damping capacity due to the negative stiffness effect.

The effect of the outliers discussed in the commentary of Fig. 11 is apparent in the average results

Fig. 8 Gas springs force and stiffness versus stroke

Fig. 9 Gas spring stroke and length variation relative to the vertical displacement u

for the 25 records regarding the displacement ratios shown in Fig. 13, in that, although the CD seemed to have an advantage over the SDA in many cases, on average the SDA is slightly more effective, even though the discrepancies are too small to be considered significant — specifically, a 2.3% difference. Regarding the comparison between the linear and non-linear SDA models, the observation is similar to the previous comparison. Their response is effectively identical since the former averages only a 1.1% lower ratio.

Fig. 10 Ratios of the peak absolute structure acceleration response A_s -to-PGA for 25 actual earthquakes. Comparison of the Non-linear SDA (red) versus the conventional damper CD (orange). X-axis index corresponding to earthquake # of Table A1 (Appendix)

Fig. 11 Ratios of the peak relative displacement response U_s normalized by the vertical static displacement X_{vsd} (20 mm) for 25 actual earthquakes. Comparison between the Non-linear SDA (red) versus the conventional damper CD (orange). X-axis index corresponding to earthquake # of Table A1 (Appendix)

Fig. 12 Average of peak seismic mass absolute acceleration to PGA ratios for the 25 earthquake records

5.2 Indicative time domain results

Next, some indicative time history results are listed for a selected earthquake, specifically the Northridge-Tarzana, which was the most extreme in terms of PGA.

Figure 14 shows the time response of the seismic mass’s absolute acceleration for the non-linear SDA and CD models in comparison with ground acceleration. The conclusions from the individual and average accelerations ratios also hold for the general time response of the systems since the mitigation effects of the SDA are apparent for the duration of the earthquake and not solely for peak values. In this case the CD amplifies ground acceleration, as seen in the two distinct peaks of a_G , whereas the SDA successfully manages to mitigate them.

The power spectral density (PSD) of the examined earthquake is also presented in Fig. 15, which indicates that although the earthquake has generally high frequency content (in relation to some of the other earthquakes), the extreme peak acceleration and overlapping with the resonant region of the CD can prove devastating.

Another reason for the choice to highlight the Northridge-Tarzana case is demonstrated in Fig. 16. Namely, that even for this most extreme case the NSE operates inside the safety stability margin, as indicated by k_{NL} .

Fig. 13 Average of peak seismic mass relative displacement to vertical static deflection ratios for the 25 earthquake records

Fig. 14 Time history response comparison of SDA and CD seismic mass acceleration relative to ground acceleration for the Northridge-Tarzana earthquake

This is further highlighted by examining the spatial response of the NSE, shown in Fig. 17, in that the vertical displacement is well within the limits of the maximum permissible displacement range. Of course, additional safeguards may be implemented in a real-world design, e.g., utilization of hard-stop limiters at specific permissible displacements.

Figure 17 also presents the exerted vertical force of the NSE as a function of the resulting displacement of the internal mass during the Northridge-Tarzana earthquake. This response is shown over the complete force curve of the NSE for the physically possible displacement range of the mechanism.

Finally, Fig. 18 compares the time response of the absolute accelerations for both the seismic and internal masses, between the linear and gas spring SDA models. Once again, the response is almost identical between them. Namely, peak values of structure acceleration are 6.7 m/s^2 for the gas spring implementation vs. 6.2 m/s^2 for the linear model, and peak values for the acceleration of the internal mass are 21.3 m/s^2 for the non-linear vs. 21.4 m/s^2 for the linear model. Moreover, the relationship between the amplitudes of the two degrees of freedom is apparent, in that the motion of the internal degree of freedom is amplified in the SDA in association with kinetic energy absorption from the seismic mass.

Fig. 15 Vertical component PSD of the Northridge-Tarzana earthquake

Fig. 16 Time history response of the NSE's equivalent stiffness during Northridge-Tarzana

6 Conclusions

This paper proposes a novel implementation of the NSE using standardized industrial-grade nitrogen gas springs as horizontal pre-stressed elastic elements in a configuration with lever arms, in place of common stiffness elements with linear elastic behavior, such as coil springs.

This proposition addresses several practical limitations that arise in the case of common spring elements, such as undesired buckling deformation and associated off-axis bending loads, the requirement for guiding mechanisms to impose necessary kinematic constraints and a reduced range of optimal performance for the desired negative stiffness value. Additionally, due to their industrial nature, gas springs provide the required predictability of performance, tested endurance features and high tolerances, while also ensuring necessary off-axis motion resistance without requiring additional guiding components.

The performance and advantages of this implementation are numerically demonstrated through a comparison across a set of 25 actual earthquake records and are explored in more detail through a case

Fig. 17 Spatial response of the NSE's vertical force and equivalent stiffness during the Northridge-Tarzana earthquake

Fig. 18 Absolute accelerations of the SDA's seismic and internal masses. Comparison between linear spring implementation and implementation via gas springs

study example. The SDA is shown to be drastically more effective than an equivalent conventional damper regarding induced accelerations on the supported structure, while displacements are comparable and maintained within reasonable limits. An additional advantage of the non-linear gas spring behavior arises in the case of larger displacements, where the negative stiffness value increases in absolute terms instead of diminishing, as in the case of an implementation with linear springs. Therefore, the damping capacity of the SDA is maintained and even slightly improved in certain cases for large deviations in the internal degree of freedom from the equilibrium position.

All the above features render the proposed configuration a promising mechanism for the implementation of NSEs. The configuration can maintain its robustness and reliability even in cases of large displacements.

Finally, the framework presented in this work can form the basis for future investigations in several directions. One of these is the suitability of the proposed SDA to other types of excitations, such as wind or explosions. Hence, exploring the range of the concept's applicability and an exploitation of the advantages related to the non-linear behavior of gas springs is recommended. Relatedly, an examination of whether an optimization method accounting for this non-linearity would yield different results regarding the design parameters and performance of the configuration.

Also, as a next stage toward the development of the proposed design, a more realistic modeling approach, including hysteretic behavior and energy dissipation capabilities of gas springs, would provide useful insights. In the same vein, temperature effects can be incorporated to examine the endurance of the long-term use of such a system. Lastly, regarding safety, the utilization of appropriate types of limiters can be explored to ensure functional stability of the mechanism, even in the most extreme conditions.

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Appendix

A list of the 25 earthquake records is cited along with the relevant information for each earthquake and the serial numbers used in the presentation of the results in the figures included in the manuscript.

Table A1 Pertinent information of the 25 earthquake records used for the performance evaluation of the SDA proposed implementation

	Earthquake	Date	Recording station	M_w	PGA (g)	R_{jb} (km)	d_t (s)	$Dur_{1.5-9.5}$ (s)	Dominant freq. (Hz)
1	Cape Mendocino	4/25/1992	Cape Mendocino	7.01	0.74	0.0	0.02	9.7	0.3
2	Chi-Chi	9/20/1999	CHY028	7.62	0.34	3.12	0.005	8.7	0.5
3	Imperial Valley	10/15/1979	El Centro Array #4	6.53	0.29	4.9	0.005	10.3	0.3
4	Northridge	1/17/1994	Simi Valley – Katherine Rd	6.69	0.40	0.0	0.01	6.7	8.5
5	Kobe	1/16/1995	Kobe University	6.9	0.45	0.9	0.01	7.0	1.4
6	L'Aquila	4/6/2009	L'Aquila -Parking	6.3	0.37	0.0	0.005	11.6	1
7	Loma Prieta	10/18/1989	BRAN	6.93	0.51	3.85	0.005	9.8	2.8
8	Landers	6/28/1992	Lucerne	7.28	0.82	2.19	0.005	13.8	13.2
9	Bam	2003	Bam	6.6	0.97	0.05	0.005	9.6	8.3
10	Northridge	1994	Rinaldi	6.7	0.852	7.1	0.01	9.1	8.0
11	Tabas	1978	Tabas	7.35	0.641	1.79	0.02	16.5	5.6
12	Chi-Chi	1999	TCU045	7.62	0.356	26.0	0.005	11.3	1.1
13	Northridge	1978	Tarzana	6.69	1	0.37	0.02	12.6	4.6
14	Kocaeli	1999	Izmit	7.51	0.145	3.62	0.005	15.1	8.1
15	Cape Mendocino	1992	Petrolia	7.01	0.15	35.1	0.02	17.7	2.2
16	Northridge	1994	Moorpark	6.69	0.14	26.4	0.02	16.1	5.3
17	Landers	1992	Coolwater	7.28	0.17	19.74	0.0039	10.6	6.8
18	San Fernando	1971	Castaic	6.61	0.167	19.33	0.01	16.8	4.9
19	Kocaeli	1999	Fatih	7.51	0.133	53.34	0.005	34.3	7.2
20	Kozani	1995	Kozani	6.4	0.073	14.13	0.005	8.6	5.4
21	Corinth	1981	Corinth	6.6	0.1111	10.27	0.01	15.4	0.9
22	Ierissos	1983	Ierissos	6.7	0.0088	65.67	0.0024	9.4	3.0
23	Kalamata	1986	Kalamata	6.2	0.2207	6.45	0.0024	6.1	4.8
24	Kozani	1995	Kastoria	6.4	0.017	47.79	0.005	15.8	1.2
25	Griva	1990	Kilkis	6.1	0.03	26.75	0.01	11.6	2.7